

THE INFLUENCE OF EXTERNAL FACTORS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF READING AND COMPREHENSION SKILLS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM**Aslanova G.,***Ganja State University**"Pedagogy and methodology of education"**teacher of the department***Mammadova V.***Ganja State University**"Pedagogy and methodology of education"**teacher of the department*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11640052>**Abstract**

In addition to internal factors specific to each child in the primary education system, several external factors also significantly affect the development of reading comprehension skills. These factors include various aspects of the child's environment, including the family, school, and community environment. Here, the positive and negative aspects of several external influences, as well as their collective and individual effectiveness, should be determined. With the innovations created by the global education system, the common and different characteristics of national and moral values have different possibilities of influencing primary school students in one way or another. The article analyzes the external factors affecting the development of reading comprehension skills in the primary education system, the influence of parents, teachers, and classmates, as well as the overall impact of society on the educational process. At the same time, the potential of students to acquire more knowledge and information is being studied since several technological achievements in the modern era have expanded access to the virtual space. The article also provides a comparative analysis of external factors that affect the development of individual skills of students and external factors that affect the collective reading comprehension process. Additionally, it highlights the utilization possibilities of the most significant resources.

Keywords: Primary education, reading comprehension, external factors, role of family in education, school environment.

Introduction. The researched topic is relevant for all eras and has a particularly important content in the conditions of a rapidly changing global education system. Differences created by information and communication technologies increase the inequality of the educational environment between countries, and also eliminate a number of existing differences. Here, the influence of mentality, natural climatic conditions, national and moral values, socio-material opportunities, state policy, existing legislation and many other factors is great. Updated pedagogical methods and quantitative-qualitative relationships of training also play an important role in the study of the influence of external factors on primary education. The relevance of the topic is also characterized by the fact that with the increase of types and methods of education, evaluation systems and the introduction of new concepts into education (distance education, inclusive education, curriculum, etc.), traditional teaching methods are rapidly losing their basic form. The scientific novelty of the subject consists of the pedagogical and psychological analysis of the technological, project-based, virtual contacts of the communicative reconciliation that occurs in the new student-parent-teacher relations. The transition of students from behind the desk to a tablet, computer, and to communicate virtually although it reduces the role of the husband, it increases the role of the family and parents. Or, on the contrary, the role of the teacher is limited to mentoring for the students involved in the project, and the importance of the students receiving collective learning with their peers increases. However, in

both cases, the teacher has a special role, and teaching is based on his potential skills in one way or another. Teachers can help increase vocabulary through the explicit teaching of word examples and word-solving strategies in a word-rich classroom context. The role of the reading, spelling, and vocabulary teacher is to help students develop "word awareness" and build an independent vocabulary across all subjects (Landaverde, 2013). There are several factors that are important to note here. One of them is related to the negative aspects of distance learning and studying at home. Parents' lack of attention when children are reading can be a factor that affects children's difficulties. The home environment is less conducive and children are more likely to play at home and with the advancement of current technology, children are more focused on playing through various electronic devices than reading books at home. In addition to these factors, the lack of interest and motivation of the students themselves is also a factor that affects the difficulty in reading (Rohimah, 2021).

Main external factors affecting primary education

Family environment. There can be various situations, such as the participation of parents, grandparents, older siblings. Parent involvement through activities such as sharing what is read, creating a rich reading environment, and providing access to books has a significant impact on reading development. The possibilities of the family environment influencing the education of children deprived of parental care decrease, and in this context other external factors come to the fore. At the

same time, the socio-economic status of the family has a significant impact on this issue. Access to educational resources, quality materials, and stable living conditions can influence reading comprehension progress.

School environment. Class size and student-teacher ratio play an important role in the school environment, which is the main place where traditional education takes place. Smaller classes and lower student-teacher ratios allow for more individualized attention and support for reading comprehension needs. The quality of training is also evident in this matter. Effective teaching strategies, a variety of reading materials, and a stimulating learning environment are critical to developing reading comprehension. It is also important to mention school resources here. Access to libraries, technology tools, and a variety of reading programs enriches the learning experience and provides diverse approaches to reading development.

Social environment. The presence of libraries and public education programs is important here. Access to free or low-cost educational programs, libraries with diverse collections, and community events that promote reading can significantly benefit students. For students, museum trips, educational exhibitions, STEAM-format programs can have a faster impact on increasing their worldview and developing reading comprehension skills. One of the most important factors here is sociocultural factors. Cultural attitudes toward reading, access to books in the mother tongue, and positive role models within the community can have a significant impact on reading motivation and engagement. Additional external factors include health and well-being, as well as the availability of reading materials in various foreign languages. Children's physical and mental health, including their vision, hearing skills, and emotional state, can affect their ability to focus and engage with reading materials. Exposing a child to multiple languages from an early age can develop cognitive skills and potentially benefit the development of reading comprehension. Understanding the influence of these external factors allows teachers, parents, and public education policy to work together to create supportive environments that help all children understand what they read. By addressing these factors through targeted interventions and initiatives, it is possible to ensure that every child has the opportunity to develop strong reading skills, an important foundation for success in school and throughout life.

Organization of pedagogical work with external factors in the development of reading and comprehension skills

Education-parent-teacher-community factors emphasize the collaborative approach needed to develop reading comprehension in primary education. Departments within a school can work together to strengthen these factors.

1. Creating a shared vision and goals. Leadership team: Regular provision of additional reading together with teachers, parents, special education, psychologist, library staff is appropriate. Semantic reading skills cannot be developed only by the teacher's external influences. It is necessary to involve the child himself and those around him (parents and peers, other teachers) in

these processes. An equally important factor, the main criterion for the development of semantic reading skills is learning to read in time (Strunina, 2023). Setting Goals: Clear, measurable goals should be set for grade level reading comprehension. Common assessments can be used to track achievement and development. Communication strategy: It is possible to develop communication channels such as parent meetings, workshops or online platforms to share goals and progress with all stakeholders. In international practice, there are various structural units related to the organization of work in primary classes, the cooperation between which greatly accelerates the development of reading comprehension skills: the curriculum unit to ensure the integration of reading comprehension into the educational system in various subjects that form the basis of humanities and social sciences; a special education unit to identify and address any learning difficulties affecting reading comprehension; a library media services section consisting of a library in electronic and paper media that caters to various reading levels and interests; a technology section to integrate technology tools (e.g. audiobooks, digital learning platforms) that improve reading comprehension, etc. In our country, it is possible to determine the effectiveness of teaching in general, and the possibilities of influencing reading and comprehension skills in particular, by creating units in this format in a certain general education school and testing them in the form of a pilot project.

2. Parent-teacher cooperation. Teacher training: Professional development workshops should be organized for teachers on effective reading comprehension strategies and techniques. The research potential of teachers is not in the presentation of ready-made knowledge, but rather in independent research in order to direct thinking (Huseynzadeh, Azizova, Aliyev, Verdiyeva, 2021). Parent-Teacher Conferences: It is important to encourage regular communication between teachers and parents, to share individual student progress and strategies parents can use at home. Here, social networks and electronic resources can be an important support. Training programs for parents: Workshops can be organized for parents on the importance of reading comprehension and practical ways to help their children at home (eg reading aloud, creating a conducive reading environment). It is possible to encourage volunteer opportunities for parents in the classroom or library, and to strengthen relationships with teachers and students (open lesson with parents).

3. Continuous monitoring and evaluation. Data analysis: It is important to regularly analyze student data from assessments, classroom observations, and surveys to identify key areas of instruction and areas for improvement. Adaptation and improvement: Based on data analysis, it is critical to adapt and systematize instructional strategies, resources, and collaborative approaches to meet students' specific learning needs and ensure successful development of reading comprehension skills. There are a number of modern pedagogical methods and methods for increasing the ability of students to make generalizations about what they read and understand, and to draw conclusions. Among them, a

number of modern methods that come to the fore include the kinesthetic learning method, the creation of interactive learning platforms (leverage technology), a pedagogical model that combines traditional classroom lectures and homework such as "flipped classrooms", etc. takes place. The kinesthetic model is a method of learning practiced in a number of Arab countries in which students use physical contact, that is, touching an object to understand what they are reading. For example, in order to better understand the description of trees and plants in the book, it is considered appropriate to organize the physical contact of students with those plants. A number of North American schools employ a model called "flipped classrooms," in which a traditional lecture is viewed at home before class and homework is completed in the classroom with an instructor present to guide students' efforts. There are also some additional services based on international education trends to promote active learning. For example, some countries such as Finland and the USA have special education services (Connect the Dots, etc.) that encourage real-world connections.

Conclusion

By fostering a collaborative environment between students, teachers, and parents through teamwork, the education-parent-teacher vector develops strong reading comprehension skills in children. becomes an effective force in their development and leads them to success in the academic field. An important factor here is not to shy away from new experiences and to test effectiveness by applying flexible practice programs. Currently, a number of tools are used to determine reading comprehension. For example, informal assessments in-

volve open discussion, meaning students are encouraged to discuss the text in their own words, analyze characters' motivations, or discuss the author's message. This reveals their understanding and cognitive potential beyond rote. Students are asked to summarize the main points, main events or main arguments of the text. It measures their ability to identify key information. To come to such a conclusion from the research it is possible that in the development of students' reading and understanding skills, not only the students themselves, but also the main external factors influencing them - teachers, parents and the school environment - should be improved. These changes will affect the complex change of society, which is the most effective external factor.

References:

1. Landaverde, C. (2013). "Factors that affect in the development of Reading Comprehension process of 4th year English major students when reading authentic texts", Main Campus, November 28th, 84 p.
2. Rohimah, S. (2021). Reading difficulties and factors affecting reading difficulties of students of grade 1 elementary school, LADU: Journal of Languages and Education. Vol. 1, No. 5, p. 189-195.
3. Strunina, O. (2023). K voprosu o probleme razvitiya navykov smyslovogo chteniya u sovremennykh shkol'nikov. Mir science, culture, education, (4 (101)), p. 113-117. doi: 10.24412/1991-5497-2023-4101-113-117.
4. Huseynzade, R., Azizova, M., Aliyev, H., Verdiyeva, M. (2021). Pedagogy. Textbook. Baku: Translator, 488 p